

acquisition feeding). None of the inoculated seedlings showed symptoms of rice ragged stunt disease. Consequently these species of insects may not be vectors of rice ragged stunt. ■

Occurrence of tungro disease in Nepal

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Rice plants with symptoms characteristic of tungro were observed in the early to mid-tillering stages at the Rice Research Station, Parwanipur, in Nepal's tarai region. The plants were stunted; some leaves, particularly the outer ones toward the tips, were bright orange-yellow. A casual examination of vectors clearly showed the predominance in the area of *Nephotettix virescens*, the most efficient tungro vector.

Insects fed on suspected material were taken to the greenhouse at Khumaltar and inoculated under protected conditions to Taichung 176 seedlings at the 3- to 4-leaf stage. Thirty percent of the seedlings reacted positively within 10 days; their symptoms were similar to those described earlier. Parwanipur is near Bihar, India, where tungro occurs. More work is under way to further characterize the virus disease. ■

Interaction of sugars on the sporulation of *Drechslera oryzae*

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Preliminary studies have indicated that mannose, starch, and sucrose enhance *D. oryzae* sporulation in Richards medium. Sporulation was not increased by arabinose, carboxycellulose, fructose, galactose, glucose, rhamnose, ribose, or xylose. Because glucose is abundant in fresh rice tissue, further experiments were conducted to compare glucose with other sugars.

The glucose concentration was varied

from 0.4 to 3.2% in a basal medium containing 2.5% of sucrose, 2.5% of mannose, and 6.5% starch. Those concentrations maximized sporulation, so they were used in the study.

Glucose at 0.4% suppressed sporulation completely in media containing 2.5% sucrose and 2.5% mannose. In a medium with 6.5% starch, 0.4% glucose failed to completely suppress sporulation but sporulation was reduced with increased glucose concentration (see table). Concentrations of more than 0.8% completely suppressed sporulation.

The effects of cellulose, glucose, and starch on sporulation were further tested, both individually and in combination because those sugars are abundant in the rice plant. Concentrations of those sugars were standardized by using maximum

mycelial growth or sporulation observed in preliminary experiments.

Sporulation was observed only in starch and in the carboxycellulose + starch combination. Sporulation was highest in the carboxycellulose + starch combination. ■

Effect of different carbon sources on sporulation of *D. oryzae*. Karnataka, India.

Carbon source and concentration	Spores (%)
Carboxycellulose (3.5%)	a
Glucose (0.8%)	a
Starch (6.5%)	88.50 x 10 ⁴
Carboxycellulose (3.5%) + glucose (0.8%)	a
Carboxycellulose (3.5%) + starch (6.5%)	102.50 x 10 ⁴
Glucose (0.8%) + starch (6.5%)	a
Carboxycellulose (3.5%) + glucose (0.8%) + starch (6.5%)	a

a = no sporulation.

Leaf blast control by seed treatment with systemic fungicides

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Leaf blast, caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, is often a serious disease in seedbeds and may severely damage dryland rice at the seedling stage. Several experiments were conducted to determine the

effectiveness of systemic fungicides as seed treatments in *P. oryzae* control. Seeds of the blast-susceptible line IR442-2-58 were treated with powder formulations of the fungicides and then either planted in soil in plastic trays and placed in blast nursery beds, or seeded directly into blast nursery beds. The seedlings were continuously exposed to *P. oryzae* spores produced on inoculated border rows of IR442-2-58. Two weeks after seeding, the plants

Effect of seed treatment with systemic fungicides on leaf blast control in rice variety IR442-2-58 at 3-6 weeks after seeding.

Treatment		Lesions ^a (mean no./seedling)			
Fungicide	Rate (g/kg seed)	3 wk	4 wk	5 wk	6 wk
CGA49104 50 WP	4	0.015	7.7	13.6	23.5
	8	0.05	2.3	5.5	8.9
	16	0.0	1.9	1.9	-
	32	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
	40	0.0	0.0	0.9	-
PP389 50 WP	16	0.0	47.1	57.6	-
	20	15.3	41.9	57.6	79.2
	32	0.2	19.4	19.6	-
	40	0.7	5.0	9.1	8.8
Thiophanate methyl	20	40.0	106.0	138.4	158.8
	40	17.5	57.7	71.0	120.5
Benomyl 50 WP	20	52.0	129.8	166.6	188.4
	40	22.6	100.5	145.3	159.0
Untreated	0	53.7	165.0	196.1	234.7

a - means no data (experiment was terminated).